

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VII, July 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

READING TEACHERS EXPERIENCES IN A BLENDED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIES IN TEACHING READING

Rizza Mae O. Roncales, MAED

Teacher

Lord Jesus Learning Institute Inc.

NCR, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Blended learning, which integrates traditional face-to-face instruction with digital tools, is increasingly being adopted in educational settings to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Despite its potential benefits, there is limited research on the specific challenges and strategies employed by reading teachers in blended learning environments, particularly in private elementary schools in the Philippines. This study addresses this gap by exploring the experiences of reading teachers at Lord Jesus Learning Institute Inc. in Quezon City, Philippines, and aims to provide a basis for developing effective strategies in teaching reading. Using a qualitative descriptive research approach, data were collected through semi-structured interviews with 12 reading teachers and direct classroom observations. The findings reveal that teachers face significant challenges, including technological limitations, time constraints, maintaining student engagement, and ensuring equitable access to resources. Teachers employ various strategies to integrate traditional and digital resources effectively, such as using online videos to complement textbooks, creating engaging multimedia presentations, and employing interactive digital platforms to enhance reading instruction. Based on these findings, the study recommends comprehensive professional development programs focused on enhancing teachers' digital literacy and pedagogical skills. Additionally, there is a need for improved technological infrastructure and equitable access to digital resources to support effective blended learning implementation. These measures can help optimize reading instruction and improve student engagement and literacy outcomes in blended learning environments. The insights gained from this research provide a solid foundation for developing tailored strategies that address the unique challenges faced by reading teachers, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of blended learning in reading education.

Keywords: blended learning, reading instruction, teacher experiences, digital integration, student engagement

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

INTRODUCTION

Reading instruction is undergoing a transformative shift with the integration of blended learning, which combines traditional face-to-face teaching with online educational tools to enhance literacy development (McLeod et al., 2023; Hamilton et al., 2023). This approach leverages digital resources, interactive platforms, and adaptive technologies to support and engage students in the reading process.

Despite its potential, blended learning presents challenges such as varying levels of digital literacy among teachers and students, difficulties in integrating technology seamlessly, and ensuring equitable access to resources (Bull et al., 2023; Hachey et al., 2023). Teachers must adapt their instructional strategies to utilize digital tools effectively while maintaining student engagement and motivation (Carnevale et al., 2022; Smith & Brown, 2022).

In the Philippines, educators are increasingly adopting blended learning to improve student engagement, foster collaborative learning, and provide personalized learning experiences (Gonzales, 2019; Ramos, 2021). However, successful implementation requires careful planning, adequate training, and reliable internet connectivity and digital devices (Roxas, 2022). Private elementary schools play a crucial role in this transition but face unique challenges that have not been extensively studied.

This research aims to explore the experiences of reading teachers in blended learning environments at Lord Jesus Learning Institute Inc. in Quezon City, Philippines. By examining the challenges, strategies, and best practices of these teachers, the study seeks to develop tailored strategies for improving reading instruction through blended learning (Chen et al., 2022; Martin et al., 2023). The findings will contribute to the optimization of blended learning for reading, ensuring high-quality literacy education for all students.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, which provides a comprehensive model for integrating technology into teaching practices. TPACK, introduced by Mishra and Koehler (2006), emphasizes the intersection of three primary forms of knowledge: Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), and Content Knowledge (CK).

Technological Knowledge (TK) involves understanding and effectively using digital tools and resources. Teachers must be proficient in using various technologies to enhance reading instruction, including online platforms, multimedia resources, and educational software (Koehler & Mishra, 2009). This proficiency enables educators to select and utilize appropriate technological tools that align with their instructional goals and the needs of their students.

Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) refers to the methods and processes of teaching. It includes strategies for engaging students, managing classrooms, and assessing learning. Effective pedagogy in a blended learning environment requires adapting traditional teaching methods to incorporate digital tools (Shulman, 1987). This involves designing instructional activities that promote critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving, thereby creating an engaging and interactive learning environment.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Content Knowledge (CK) is the understanding of the subject matter itself. For reading instruction, it includes knowledge of literacy development, reading comprehension strategies, and methods to improve reading fluency and vocabulary acquisition (Ball, Thames, & Phelps, 2008). Strong CK enables teachers to create coherent and engaging lessons that build on students' prior knowledge and guide them toward a deeper understanding of the subject.

The TPACK framework is critical in understanding how teachers can integrate technology into their reading instruction effectively, ensuring that technological tools are used in ways that enhance learning and engagement. By combining TK, PK, and CK, educators can develop comprehensive instructional strategies that leverage the strengths of both traditional and digital resources, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of blended learning in reading education.

Figure 1. The TPACK Framework

Related Literature Review

Challenges in Blended Learning (Technological Knowledge)

Blended learning environments pose significant challenges related to technological knowledge. Teachers often struggle with technological limitations such as unreliable internet connections and insufficient technological infrastructure (Johnson, 2023). Additionally, varying levels of digital literacy among teachers can hinder the effective integration of digital tools into the curriculum (Bull et al., 2023). Addressing these challenges requires robust professional development and ongoing technical support (Carnevale et al., 2022).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p. 243-254 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Strategies for Integrating Traditional and Digital Resources (Pedagogical Knowledge)

Effective blended learning strategies require a seamless integration of traditional and digital resources. Teachers must develop innovative lesson plans that leverage digital tools to complement face-to-face instruction. Research indicates that interactive multimedia presentations, online quizzes, and digital storytelling can enhance student engagement and comprehension (Ghimire, 2022). The integration of these tools should be aligned with pedagogical goals to maximize their impact on student learning (Smith & Brown, 2022).

Assessing the Impact on Student Engagement and Reading Skills (Content Knowledge)

The impact of blended learning on student engagement and reading skills is a critical area of assessment. Studies have shown that blended learning can improve student motivation and participation by providing personalized and interactive learning experiences (Gonzales, 2019). Tools such as digital reading platforms and online assessments allow for continuous monitoring of student progress, enabling teachers to tailor instruction to meet individual needs (Ramos, 2021). However, ensuring that all students have equitable access to these resources remains a significant challenge (Hachey et al., 2023).

The research paradigm in Figure 2 shows how the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework impacts blended learning strategies for reading instruction. TPACK combines Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), and Content Knowledge (CK) to enhance teaching with technology. TK involves using digital tools and resources effectively, such as digital platforms, software, and devices. Challenges include technological limitations and varying levels of proficiency among teachers. PK includes teaching strategies, engaging students, managing classrooms, and assessing progress. In blended learning, it means designing lessons that combine traditional and digital resources while maintaining student engagement. CK refers to understanding the subject matter, like literacy development and reading strategies, ensuring that instructional materials are accurate and accessible to students.

Teachers face several challenges in implementing blended learning, including the time and effort required for planning, technological proficiency, equitable access to technology, and maintaining student engagement. Younger students, in particular, struggle with self-regulation and using digital platforms independently. Innovative assessment strategies are also needed to measure both online and offline learning activities. To address these challenges, teachers use strategies that blend traditional and digital resources effectively. This might include using digital storytelling tools alongside traditional reading assignments or integrating interactive e-books with printed texts. These strategies help increase student motivation and participation and improve reading skills.

Based on these findings, the paradigm suggests recommendations for teaching reading in blended learning environments. Educators can develop best practices and strategies to optimize technology use in reading instruction, aiming to enhance student engagement, improve reading skills, and ensure equitable access to resources. This approach creates a more effective and inclusive educational experience.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to explore the experiences of reading teachers in a blended learning environment at Lord Jesus Learning Institute Inc. in Quezon City, Philippines, with the goal of developing effective strategies for teaching reading. Specifically, the study sought to address the following research questions:

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

1. What were the challenges faced by teachers in the development and implementation of blended learning for reading instruction in the elementary school setting?
2. What strategies did teachers employ to integrate traditional and digital resources effectively in a blended learning environment?
3. How did educators assess the impact of blended learning on students' engagement and reading skills?
4. Based on the findings, what strategies in teaching reading could be recommended for blended learning environments?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative descriptive research approach to explore reading teachers' experiences in blended learning environments. This method was suitable for capturing the complexities of teachers' experiences, behaviors, and interactions that were not easily quantifiable (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

The study was conducted at Lord Jesus Learning Institute Inc. in Quezon City, Philippines. The participants included 12 reading teachers who were selected through purposive sampling based on their involvement in reading instruction and experience with blended learning. This ensured that the participants had relevant knowledge and experience crucial to the study (Johnson, 2023).

Semi-structured interviews and direct observations were used as the primary research instruments. The interview guide was developed to elicit detailed responses about the participants' experiences, challenges, strategies, and assessments related to blended learning. The use of direct observations provided additional insights into classroom practices and the integration of technology (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Data collection involved obtaining necessary permissions from the school administration and conducting an orientation session for participants. Semi-structured interviews were scheduled and conducted with the teachers, and these interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim for accuracy. Observations were also conducted to complement the interview data (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. This involved transcribing the interviews, coding the data, and identifying recurring themes and patterns. The analysis focused on understanding the challenges, strategies, and impacts of blended learning on reading instruction. Constant comparison was used to ensure robustness and coherence in the interpretation of findings (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

Ethical considerations were strictly adhered to, including obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and allowing voluntary participation. The research procedures were validated by experts to ensure reliability and trustworthiness, and participants' identities were anonymized to protect their privacy (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p. 243-254 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges, strategies, and impacts associated with implementing blended learning for reading instruction in a private elementary school setting. By analyzing the experiences of reading teachers, several key themes emerged, offering insights into the practicalities of integrating traditional and digital learning resources.

Challenges Faced by Teachers in the Development and Implementation of Blended Learning for Reading Instruction in the Elementary School Setting

Teachers in this study identified several challenges in implementing blended learning for reading instruction. Technological limitations, such as unreliable internet connections and inadequate infrastructure, were major obstacles. Teachers also reported difficulties in using digital tools effectively due to varying levels of digital literacy among both teachers and students. Time constraints for planning and managing blended learning activities were another significant challenge. Teachers expressed that the additional time required for integrating technology into the curriculum often left them feeling overwhelmed. Furthermore, maintaining student engagement in a blended learning environment was challenging, especially when students had to study independently online. Issues of equitable access to digital resources also exacerbated existing educational disparities, making it difficult to ensure all students received the same quality of instruction.

Strategies Teachers Employ to Integrate Traditional and Digital Resources Effectively in a Blended Learning Environment

To overcome these challenges, teachers employed various strategies to integrate traditional and digital resources effectively. One common approach was using online videos and digital storytelling tools to complement textbooks and traditional reading materials. This strategy helped make lessons more engaging and interactive. Teachers also created multimedia presentations and utilized interactive platforms to maintain student interest and participation. They planned lessons that blended traditional and digital resources, ensuring that the digital components reinforced the content covered in face-to-face instruction. Additionally, teachers emphasized the importance of careful selection and evaluation of digital tools to ensure they aligned with pedagogical goals and enhanced learning outcomes.

Assessment of Blended Learning Impact on Engagement and Reading Skills

Blended learning had a significant impact on student engagement. Teachers reported that incorporating digital tools and interactive activities increased student motivation and participation. Online quizzes, discussion forums, and multimedia content were particularly effective in maintaining student interest and promoting active learning. However, challenges remained in keeping students engaged during independent online study sessions. Teachers noted that younger students, in particular, struggled with self-regulation and needed more guidance and support to stay focused.

The impact of blended learning on reading skills was generally positive. Teachers observed improvements in students' reading comprehension, fluency, and

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

vocabulary acquisition. The use of digital reading platforms allowed for personalized learning experiences, enabling students to progress at their own pace and receive immediate feedback on their performance. However, assessing these improvements was challenging due to the variability in students' access to digital resources and the need for innovative assessment strategies that captured both online and offline learning activities.

Professional Development Needs in Blended Learning

Teachers identified a strong need for professional development focused on digital literacy and the effective integration of technology into reading instruction. They expressed a desire for training programs that provided practical, hands-on experience with digital tools and platforms. Additionally, teachers highlighted the need for ongoing support and resources to help them stay updated with the latest technological advancements and pedagogical strategies.

Preferred Modes of Professional Development

The preferred modes of professional development included workshops, online courses, and peer collaboration. Teachers valued opportunities for collaborative learning, where they could share experiences and best practices with their colleagues. They also appreciated online courses that offered flexibility and allowed them to learn at their own pace. Mentorship programs were another preferred mode, providing personalized guidance and support from experienced educators.

Assessment of Implementation of Blended Learning

The assessment of the implementation of blended learning revealed mixed results. While many teachers successfully integrated digital tools into their reading instruction, challenges remained in ensuring consistent and equitable access to technology for all students. Teachers reported that blended learning enhanced student engagement and reading skills, but they also noted the need for more comprehensive professional development and support systems to optimize its effectiveness. Continuous monitoring and adjustment of instructional practices were essential to address the evolving challenges and opportunities presented by blended learning.

This study explored the experiences of reading teachers in a blended learning environment at Lord Jesus Learning Institute Inc. in Quezon City, Philippines. The findings revealed several key challenges and strategies related to the implementation of blended learning for reading instruction. Teachers reported major obstacles, including unreliable internet connections, inadequate technological infrastructure, varying levels of digital literacy among both teachers and students, significant time constraints in planning and managing blended learning activities, and difficulties in maintaining student engagement during independent online study sessions. Ensuring equitable access to digital resources was also a challenge, exacerbating existing educational disparities.

To overcome these challenges, teachers employed various strategies to integrate traditional and digital resources effectively. They used online videos and digital

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p. 243-254 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

storytelling tools to complement traditional reading materials, created multimedia presentations, and utilized interactive platforms to maintain student interest and participation. Careful selection and evaluation of digital tools were essential to ensure alignment with pedagogical goals.

The impact of blended learning on student engagement and reading skills was generally positive. Teachers reported increased student motivation and participation due to the use of digital tools and interactive activities. Improvements were also observed in students' reading comprehension, fluency, and vocabulary acquisition. However, assessing these improvements was challenging due to variability in students' access to digital resources.

Teachers identified a strong need for professional development focused on digital literacy and effective integration of technology. They preferred professional development modes such as workshops, online courses, and peer collaboration. While blended learning enhanced student engagement and reading skills, consistent and equitable access to technology remained a challenge.

Conclusions

The study concluded that while blended learning has significant potential to enhance reading instruction, several challenges must be addressed to optimize its effectiveness. Technological limitations, varying levels of digital literacy, and time constraints are major obstacles that hinder the seamless integration of blended learning. Despite these challenges, teachers employ innovative strategies to integrate traditional and digital resources, resulting in improved student engagement and reading skills. There is a critical need for comprehensive professional development programs to support teachers in effectively utilizing digital tools and resources. Addressing these challenges and providing ongoing support can significantly enhance the implementation and outcomes of blended learning in reading instruction.

Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness of blended learning in reading instruction, it is recommended to invest in reliable internet connections and adequate technological infrastructure to support blended learning. Develop comprehensive professional development programs focused on digital literacy and effective integration of technology in reading instruction, and offer workshops, online courses, and peer collaboration opportunities to support continuous learning and adaptation. Provide targeted training for both teachers and students to improve digital literacy skills and ensure all students have equitable access to digital resources to avoid exacerbating educational disparities. Implement continuous monitoring and assessment strategies to evaluate the effectiveness of blended learning and make necessary adjustments. Foster a collaborative learning environment where teachers can share best practices and support each other in navigating the complexities of blended learning.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p. 243-254 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

References

- Ball, D. L., Thames, M. H., & Phelps, G. (2008). Content knowledge for teaching: What makes it special? *Journal of Teacher Education*, 59(5), 389-407.
- Bonk, C. J., & Graham, C. R. (2019). *The handbook of blended learning: Global perspectives, local designs*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bower, M., et al. (2022). Trends and strategies for online and blended learning. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 18(2), 45-60.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. Sage.
- Bull, G., et al. (2023). Challenges of digital literacy in blended learning environments. *Journal of Digital Education*, 10(2), 34-48.
- Carnevale, D., et al. (2022). Technological integration in education: Barriers and solutions. *Educational Technology Review*, 15(1), 23-36.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., et al. (2019). Digital competence in knowledge society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 12(3), 23-40.
- Garrison, D. R., & Kanuka, H. (2020). Blended learning: Uncovering its transformative potential in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 13(3), 21-27.
- Ghimire, B. (2022). Integrating digital tools in traditional teaching. *Teaching and Learning Journal*, 11(1), 89-102.
- Gonzales, M. (2019). Blended learning in Philippine elementary schools: A case study. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 12(2), 45-59.
- Hachey, A., et al. (2023). Addressing educational disparities in blended learning. *International Journal of Educational Equity*, 19(1), 78-93.
- Hew, K. F., & Cheung, W. S. (2021). Blended learning: Research perspectives, volume 2. *International Journal of Instructional Media*, 39(1), 5-15.
- Johnson, S. (2023). Challenges of blended learning in reading instruction. *International Journal of Reading Education*, 22(4), 67-80.
- Kim, C. & Kim, M. K. (2023). Effective strategies for blended learning in elementary education. *Journal of Educational Research*, 18(3), 101-115.
- Kim, P., & Park, H. (2021). Challenges and solutions in blended learning implementation. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 69(1), 27-43.
- Koehler, M. J., & Mishra, P. (2009). What is technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK)? *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 60-70.
- Lowenthal, P. R., & Hodges, C. B. (2020). In search of quality: Using quality matters to analyze the quality of massive, open, online courses (MOOCs). *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(5), 83-101.
- Means, B., et al. (2019). Evaluating the effectiveness of online and blended learning programs. *Educational Researcher*, 42(4), 258-268.
- Picciano, A. G. (2019). Blended learning: Implications for growth and access. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 12(1), 95-102.
- Ramos, A. (2021). Personalized learning in blended environments: *The Philippine context*. *Educational Innovations in the Philippines*, 9(2), 89-104.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p. 243-254 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

- Shulman, L. S. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1-22.
- Smith, R., & Brown, E. (2022). Effective engagement strategies in blended learning. *Learning and Instruction*, 34(2), 150-165.
- Vaughan, N., et al. (2020). *Teaching in blended learning environments: Creating and sustaining communities of inquiry*. Athabasca University Press.
- Weinberger, A., et al. (2020). Cognitive processes in blended learning environments. *Educational Psychologist*, 53(4), 271-292.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13149204

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.